

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution

Task 2.1

Summarising the possibilities and needs of candidate Certified Reference Materials for plastic in solid, liquid and gaseous matrices

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Executive Summary

Worldwide demand for quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of analyses of micro- and nanoplastic particles (MNP) in water, air, sediment, biological tissues and other matrices is steadily increasing with awareness, stewardship initiatives and legislation surrounding the issues of plastic particle pollution. A key QA/QC tool is the certified reference material (CRM). The analysis of plastic particles in technical and environmental systems as well as biological matrices is still in early stages of technical readiness and no standardized methods are available to date. The production of CRMs for plastic particles is hampered by a lack of metrologically validated procedures. However, as the analytical science of MNP advances and MNP interlaboratory studies are showing that more and more laboratories are becoming proficient in analysing MNP, CRMs should be added to the QA/QC toolbox. This study aims at identifying the scope of current CRM needs, the technical feasibility of meeting these needs, and suggests a practical way forward for the development of CRMs for plastic particles.

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Definition
CRM	Certified reference material
EM	Electron microscopy
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
GC	Gaschromatography
HRMS	High resolution mass spectrometry
LC	Liquid chromatography
MS	Massspectrometry
MNP	Micro- and nanoplastic particles
MP	Microplastic particle
NP	nanoplastic particle
PA	Polyamide
PC	Polycarbonate
PE	Polyethylene
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PMB	Polymer Modified Bitumens
PP	Polypropylene
PS	Polystyrene
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
SCCWRP	Southern California Coastal Water Research Project
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
QA/QC	Quality assurance and quality control
WP	Work Package

Acronyms	Definition
EC	European Commission
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
EU	European Union
ISO	International Standards Organization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NIVA	Norsk institutt for vannforskning
NORMAN	Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances
VU	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

1. Introduction

Worldwide demand for quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) of analyses of micro- and nanoplastic particles (MNP) in water, air, sediment, biological tissues and other matrices is steadily increasing with increasing awareness, stewardship initiatives and legislation surrounding the issues of plastic particle pollution. Validation of MNP analytical methods requires attention to many QA/QC issues such as the determination of blanks, reproducibility, repeatability, recovery, accuracy and precision (Silva et al., 2018; Wagner et al., 2022). Certified reference materials (CRMs) are key QA/QC tools for the validation of analytical methods. A CRM is a *'reference material characterized by a metrologically valid procedure for one or more specified properties, accompanied by a reference material certificate that provides the value of the specified property, its associated uncertainty, and a statement of metrological traceability'* (ISO, 2016).

The analysis of MNP in environmental, and biological matrices is still in early stages and no standardized methods have been adopted to date. The production of CRMs for plastic particles is hampered by a lack of suitable metrologically validated procedures. However, as the analytical science of MNP advances (Ly et al., 2022; Ye et al., 2022) and MNP interlaboratory studies (Isobe et al., 2019; Lares et al., 2019; van Mourik et al., 2021) are showing that laboratories are becoming increasingly proficient in analysing MNP calling for the inclusion of CRMs into the QA/QC toolbox.

This study set out to identify the scope of current CRM needs in the analytical community, the technical feasibility of meeting these needs, and to suggest a practical way forward for the development of CRMs for MNP analyses. We focused mainly on Europe as CRMs are often marketed regionally and less intercontinentally. The quest to develop a MNP-CRM in a complex (environmental, biological) matrix requires a dedicated, multi-year effort of collaborators with a variety of expertise and analytical capacities. Because CRMs in complex matrices need to be fit-for-purpose for the users in the field, the development is best approached in a participatory manner, and can benefit from sharing plans in an early stage, as we do here.

2. Approach

When producing CRMs for a novel target analyte class, many considerations on user groups, materials and methods, and technical requirements need to be made in order to come to a decision on designing the fit-for-purpose CRMs (Figure 1). For this we first asked market research types of questions, i.e. who needs CRMs and for what matrices and concentration ranges, particle size ranges, and polymer types would they use them? We then collected information on the current and expected MNP major research and monitoring programs using methods for which CRMs could be useful. A scan of microplastics project initiatives world-wide was performed to gain insight into the current and newly emerging matrix types, analytical methods and studies on the horizon. The scope covered an approximate timespan of the coming decade (i.e., 2022-2032). Lastly, we explored the production requirements and technical and economic feasibility through an inventory of production criteria, potential obstacles and challenges to producing matrix CRMs for MNPs, with ideas of how to mitigate potential risks to the production process.

Figure 1. Considerations for designing and prioritizing production of fit-for-purpose natural-matrix CRMs for MNP. PT = proficiency testing.

Initial input was gathered from seven potential MNP-CRM users at laboratories at universities (n=2), national institutes (n=4), as well as an analytical standards company (n=1). Based on this input, a proposal was made and presented to an additional ca. 40 laboratories in the field participating in the QUASIMEME-NORMAN-VUA-NIVA MNP interlaboratory study and the JRC-Geel for feedback. The response was incorporated into the report, as described below.

The aim of the overall exercise was to identify viable options to produce CRMs. This was guided by how preferred candidate matrix CRM designs scored on criteria of:

- i. Large market for the CRM (due to research and monitoring programs, risk assessments, industrial applications, and growth in various research areas).
- ii. Technically feasible to produce and transport internationally.
- iii. Availability of clean matrix to spike or alternatively a natural material.
- iv. Availability of high quality, stable spiking materials of the desired polymer type(s), size(s), shape(s) and quality.
- v. Suitability for mass spectrometry-based techniques (mass determination of polymers).
- vi. Suitability for Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) (and Raman) based techniques (polymer particle counting).

When all the input had been gathered, a list of potential natural-matrix CRMs was established, with polymer types, concentration ranges and sizes. A stepwise approach was taken to narrow in on the

CRMs from high to low priority. The rationale for the choices made supported the selection. The analysis of was designed to collect arguments based on these considerations for selection of the matrix and what exactly should be in it to make it most effective.

Next, a feasibility scan was performed for both technical and financial feasibility of creating the CRMs deemed needed for the market over the coming decade (from ca. 2022). The availability and technical capacity to create clean matrices was assessed, followed by an inventory of MNP reference materials for spiking. This resulted in a prioritized list of options for 2 candidate CRMs. These were then assessed for suitability for both polymer mass and particle counting techniques currently in use for MNP analyses.

The final selection of priority CRMs was then narrowed down further to two candidate CRMs for suitability for mass determination and particle counting techniques.

3. Results

3.1. Market for MNP CRMs

We made an inventory of MNP monitoring programs both existing and planned, but also which user 'markets' are expected to open up for CRMs in the next 5-10 years (although CRM production is typically not a commercial endeavour). The main focus being on MNP CRMs for environmental research, it is not uncommon for some CRMs to be applied across different sectors (e.g., CRMs for contaminant analysis in environmental biota and food safety). CRM markets in general are small markets; user groups tend to be highly specialised and low in number. We identified three user groups interested in CRMs for the MNP in natural matrix: commercial, government and research (private or academic) laboratories. Commercial laboratories, including instrument makers, may use CRMs for industrial applications (e.g., MNP in biota may be applicable in food quality research). Government laboratories have CRM needs for measurements within monitoring programs and exposure assessments. Research done privately or in academia also need CRMs to validate novel MNP preparation and measurement protocols and show proficiency.

Furthermore, we identified several potential drivers of the production of CRM without being direct users. Such drivers include, e.g., European directives for Drinking Water, Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Circular Economy, Plastics Strategy, Green Deal, Cosmetics Directive, etc.

In addition, anchoring MNP levels in (supra)governmental policies, will strongly increase the needs for MNP CRMs.

The market research also provided an inventory of other MNP CRM development initiatives and we discovered two other initiatives, including one led by European Commission Joint Research Centre (EU-JRC) (Geel, Belgium) and one led by Southern California Coastal Water Research Project (SCCWRP) in collaboration with Californian Water Board. JRC has produced one candidate CRM for MNPs in water, consisting of a cryo-milled polyethylene terephthalate (PET) delivered as a salt (NaCl) cake in a vial to be dissolved by the practitioner in water (Seghers et al., 2022). This material has already been used in an interlaboratory study. The other initiative used capsules filled with CaCO₃ and lactic acid soda and the six most used plastics (PE, PET, PS, PVC, PC and PP).

When thinking of the unit volume required for MNP CRMs, we looked to trends in other environmental contaminant CRMs. The most popular environmental matrix CRMs are used at a rate of 200-250 units a year, e.g., JRC has two PM₁₀ CRMs (certified for PAH or heavy metals), that serve the largest CRM user groups. However, CRM developers may prefer to produce at least 1000 units of each material, otherwise production costs become prohibitive. Best-seller, fast-moving CRMs can reach tenfold higher unit volumes, but these are not CRMs in the environmental pollution realm, but rather more typical for clinical and health markets.

When designing CRMs for a specific purpose, the possibility of satisfying the needs of users from other sectors should also be kept in mind. While the focus here should be on environmental matrices, some could conceivably be used by users from other sectors, as long as the methods applied are appropriate. It is common for CRM users to use the 'next best thing' if the exact natural matrix they are using is not available. While designing for cross-sectoral use is not a top priority in CRM design for the environmental MNP analyses, it is indeed something that is taken into consideration to keep it open as long as other constraints and priorities do not override it.

3.2. Selection of natural matrix for CRM

The ranking of the importance of the different matrices for CRM was based on users in Europe but also included an assessment of the global need for these materials. Several factors such as the availability of reference matrix materials, the stability of the reference materials, the storage conditions and the shelf life of the matrix materials, and the techniques for mixing the MNP with the matrix material were taken into consideration.

The rationale for the different sample matrices is summarized in Table 1. The users of each matrix are heavily reflected by the type of matrix as many institutes are specialized e.g., in different environments, e.g., aquatic and marine (e.g., water, sediment, suspended matter), terrestrial (soil), air quality. There may also be a focus on biological samples for certain other potential users in these areas.

Table 1. MNP-CRM matrix options with rationale estimated for the decade 2022-2032 based on input from consortium.

Natural matrix	Rationale
Air	- The presence of MNP in air will be very important when assessing possible impacts of MNP on human / animal health on a long term.
Biota	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The presence of MNP in animals (e.g. fish for food supply) or even in humans will be very important when assessing possible impacts of MNP on human / animal health on a long term. - The uptake of MNP into biota most likely will drive eco-toxicological impacts. Thus, MNP materials in such matrices will be key for QA/QC for respective monitoring programs. - Increasing interest in MNP analyses in biota. There are already 635 articles in Scopus (Feb. 2022). This number is increasing year by year.
(Drinking) water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The presence of MNP in drinking water will be very important when assessing possible impacts of MNP on human / animal health on a long term. - Water seems to be the major carrier of MNP particles.
Food products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MNP particles will likely be 'discovered' in many processed (powdered) food products. Labs offering MNP analyses in food products will therefore need a suitable reference material. - Studying MNP particles in food products is important for food safety control.
Sediment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sediment is one of the most studied matrices, since it provides relevant environmental information. - Sediment is a stable compartment. It is therefore most likely to yield reproducible results. - Sediment is an important sink for MNP. It is a compartment where most likely plastic will end up.
Sewage sludge	- MNP are discharged to sewer systems and accumulated in sewage sludge during the wastewater treatment. Sewage sludge therefore represents a key matrix where MNP will be accumulated.
Soil (agricultural)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agricultural soils may become hotspots for plastic pollution, due to the use of poorly degradable mulch foils. Therefore, MNP in an agricultural soil matrix will be required for QA/QC purposes for agricultural soil 'screening' projects. - MNP in soil are important to assess potential sources. It provides relevant environmental information. - Soil is a stable compartment. It is therefore most likely to yield reproducible results. - Soil is a compartment where most likely plastic will end up.

3.3. Polymer types and particle sizes and concentrations

CRMs may contain mixtures of several polymer types present in plastic materials, and matrices at different concentrations. Based on the feedback to the questionnaire, 7 polymer types were identified as highest priority (Table 2), and different sizes and size classes were indicated by the consortium to be most important to include in the MNP-CRM matrix (Table 3).

It is important for CRMs to be either naturally occurring samples that are stable and homogenous to use as is or alternatively, relatively clean natural materials need to be spiked at realistic concentrations in order to be of most use. The concentration for different polymers in environmental samples range from below actual detection limits to several orders of magnitude above the detection limits, depending on geographical location and aspects of point sources.

Table 2. The most needed polymer types for the MNP-CRMS with rationale estimated for the decade 2022-2032 based on input from consortium.

Polymer type	Rationale
Polyamide (PA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detected in sediment, originating from fibbers. - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: biota, (drinking) water, sediment, etc.
Polycarbonate (PC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: biota, sediment, etc.
Polyethylene (PE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the most detected polymers in biota. - The most frequently detected polymer in sediment originating from fibbers. Concentrations are highly variable, therefore the mean concentration of relevant publications. - In soil PE concentrations are highly variable, therefore the mean concentration of relevant publications. - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: air, biota (e.g. Algae), (drinking) water, sediment, sewage sludge, (Agricultural) soil etc. - Amongst others relevant because of tire particles, as microfibers, as well as virgin as weathered.
PET	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: air, biota (e.g. Algae), drinking water, sediment, sewage sludge, (Agricultural) soil etc. - Amongst others relevant because of tire particles, as microfibers, as well as virgin as weathered.
Polypropylene (PP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One of the most detected polymers in biota. - In soil PP concentrations are highly variable, therefore the mean concentration of relevant publications. - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: air, biota (e.g. Algae), (drinking) water, sediment, sewage sludge, (Agricultural) soil etc. - Amongst others relevant because of tire particles, as microfibers, as well as virgin as weathered.
Polystyrene (PS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: biota, sediment, etc.
Polyvinyl chloride (PVC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant polymer for multiple matrices: biota (e.g. Algae), (drinking) water, sediment, sewage sludge, (Agricultural) soil etc.

Table 3. The most needed particle sizes with rationale to include in the MNP-CRM matrix options, estimated for the decade 2022-2032 based on input from consortium.

Particle size or size range	Rationale
200 µm	Maximum size
50 µm	a size, which is clearly detectable by FTIR
20 µm	A size that is a bit more challenging for FTIR
5 µm	To go lower to eventually this size class
500nm	Good size to analyse with Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)
50 nm	Good size to analyse with Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)
300 µm - 500 µm	Generally, the most used plastic polymers size range for analyses of PE, PP, PS, PET, PC, PVC, PA in Marine softbottom sediment
20 µm - 300 µm	Generally, the most used plastic polymers size range for analyses of PE, PP, PS, PET, PC, PVC, PA in biota and sediment.
1 µm - 20 µm	Generally, the most used plastic polymers size range for analyses of PE, PP, PS, PET, PC, PVC, PA for drinking water.
< 1 mm	For several matrices for Tire, Polymer Modified Bitumens (PMB) and road markings.
<400 µm	Tires and PMB expected to be found in sizes <400 µm.
20/ 30 µm (or even smaller) - 5 mm	For road markings which can be found in a large range of sizes as they continue to fragment in the environment.
10 µm- 1 mm	For analyses of PE and PP in sediment and soil.
100 nm-100 µm	For analyses of PE, PP and PET in air.

3.4. Analytical Methods

The full analytical method from sample preparation steps through to analytical detection and quantification are a key factor to take into consideration when designing a matrix CRM. Ideally, CRMs should be universal and applicable for all methods, and there is a danger that a given CRM design will favour certain methods above others, and even potentially exclude some methods, e.g., by designing a CRM with plastic nanoparticles any method that cannot target submicron particles is excluded.

With what purpose are the analytical methods applied? For selected methods, particle counting and characterizing particles on an individual particle level e.g., by shape, colour, size, and molecular structure, is of prime importance. In (nano)toxicology, there is a strong need to develop nanoplastic CRMs optimized for particle counting, as the particle number seems to be of key importance. In environmental pollution research, mass flow analyses are frequently used to assess major pathways of pollutants of interest. To confirm the results from such studies and also to establish mass fluxes within individual and across different environmental compartments the mass of plastics is the key measurand. In air quality studies and monitoring databases the mass of airborne particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5 data) is targeted. However, besides designing a CRM that suits only polymer mass determination methods, there is also a need for standard materials for particular sizes, shapes, and or colour determination. The methods and the priority ranking extracted from the questionnaire is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Analytical methods that the MNP-CRM matrix options need to serve, estimated for the decade 2022-2032. Priority ranking (high/med/low) based on input from consortium.

Analytical method	Rationale for the priority ranking	Priority ranking
Pyrolysis- Gaschromatography / Massspectrometry (GC/MS)	Degree of automation, microplastic particles (MPs) and nanoplastic particles (NPs) can be analysed	High
μ-FTIR	The degree of automation and the speed on analyses	High
Raman	Highly complementary to the mass based thermal desorption GC-MS techniques	Medium
TEM, SEM	For the NPs, electron microscopy (EM) may be very powerful, however not many labs apply EM	Medium
Liquid chromatography -high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS)	Suitable for NP analysis.	Medium

3.5. CRM Production feasibility and technical requirements

One of the most challenging issues is to assess whether the polymeric particles are evenly distributed within the matrix. Depending on the size of the particles, they may have to be spiked to the matrix in either powdered or suspended forms. The stability of the suspension must also be assessed.

For different instrumentation (particle counting and mass determination), difference in technical requirements may become important. This is due to differences in the target particle size ranges as well as of course how the true concentrations are reported for the test material.

4. Proposal for a natural-matrix MNP CRM

The feedback from the questionnaire described above resulted in the selection of two top priorities for the CRM production based on criteria (Table 5). Both materials will be slated for production in the H2020 EUROqCHARM project (2020-2023) based on the ability to meet the criteria set out at the beginning of this study.

Table 5. Summary of rationale for two natural matrix CRMs options.

	CRM 1	CRM 2
Natural matrix selected:	Sediment or fine sand	Biota (i.e. Muscle or algae)
Particles spiked - Polymer types	PA, PC, PE, PET, PP, PS, PVC	PA, PC, PE, PET, PP, PS, PVC
Particles spiked - Particle sizes in μm	50 μm - 1 mm	50 μm - 1 mm
Analytical methods relevant to the CRM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Micro FTIR - Pyrolysis GC/MS - Raman - SEM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Micro FTIR - Pyrolysis GC/MS - Raman - SEM
Market aspects	e.g. monitoring programs, risk assessments, and growth in various research areas	e.g. monitoring programs, risk assessments, and growth in various research areas
Availability of clean matrix to spike	Sediment can be burned and then spiked. Quartz sand can be acid washed and sieved to the desired size	

5. Conclusions

Developing two fit-for-purpose natural-matrix CRMs to support quality-controlled MNP analysis is an massive task that requires user input at multiple points along the way. The selection for [CRM1] and [CRM2] is intended to serve the users of the analytical MNP community for natural matrices of current and future interest. They furthermore address the main polymer types applied in contemporary high production volume plastic material applications at size ranges and concentrations that are useful for laboratories to utilize for the validation of methods for both thermal desorption GC/MS approaches (polymer mass determination), and for particle counting techniques such as FTIR and Raman which are currently the most popular techniques.

Matrix MNP CRMs are critical for research, especially in a phase where labs have no access to materials with each other and compare their methods in the development phase. Therefore, even making a start at producing these materials – even with indicative values - can make a valuable contribution to the nascent field of MNP QA/QC tools. CRM development is a long process by which is important to start to provide materials as soon as possible, to learn by doing. When the analytical methods are ready then it's time to start to produce certified values.

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Appendix 1: Survey sent out to EUROqCHARM Partners

Task 2.1 Summarising the possibilities and needs of candidate CRMs for plastic in solid, liquid and gaseous matrices

Amsterdam, 3 February 2021

Internal project report (to be developed and finalized between Feb and May 2021)

Goal: Inventory of needs, opportunities and priorities for matrix CRMs for MNP.

Instructions/Next steps:

- 1) Each Partner organization: NIVA, CHRION, NILU, CSIC, EAWAG, AFNOR, IFREMER, is requested to provide 1 document to VUA with a response to the questions in the survey table below (1 version per partner organization for those working in pairs) and **return to** heather.leslie@vu.nl
- 2) **no later than 22 February 2021.**
- 3) Heather (VUA) will collate the input in a draft report (March).
- 4) Partners are asked for further feedback on this draft report (April).
- 5) Finalize the internal report (May).

Authors/contributors invited to participate (as agreed on day of WP2 kickoff):

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Survey of EUROqCHARM Partners' *a priori* Opinions on Certified Reference Materials for analysis of novel plastic particle analytes in matrices: needs, opportunities, priorities

1. Please provide your organisation's expert opinion.
2. Please also indicate if your partner organization cannot form an opinion at this time, or if you are uncertain of the answer.
It is not a problem if you do not have an answer to every question; in these cases, simply indicate what kind of information is missing/would be needed to bring more certainty.

Abbreviations

MNP = micro- and nanoplastic particles; CRM = certified reference material

Matrix CRM = CRM consisting of MNP in a sample matrix (as opposed to an analytical standard)

Name(s) of respondent and partner organisation: [insert names here]

QUESTIONS	Please write your answers in this column. Please be concise. If your answer is unknown/uncertain, please just indicate this + what kind of information would be needed to reduce the uncertainty.
<p>1. MNP matrix-CRM market: List key examples of important MNP-matrix-CRM user groups and major MNP monitoring/assessment programmes which would purchase CRMs for MNP, if they were to become available.</p>	<p>Microplastics</p>
<p>2. Your preferences for top 4 matrix choices, in order of which should be produced first to last. You may add others to the list e.g. for long term, or small markets.</p>	<p>Matrix Choice 1: Matrix Choice 2: Matrix Choice 3: Matrix Choice 4: Other Matrices of interest (e.g. on longer term, small niche markets):</p>

<p>3. For each matrix choice (listed in Q2) give argument(s) why it should be prioritized?</p> <p><i>Think about all possible reasons to prioritize. Think not only about your own lab situation but also the larger MNP analytical <u>landscape</u>.</i></p>	<p>Matrix Choice 1 is a priority because:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 2:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 3:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 4:</p> <p>Other:</p>
<p>4. Briefly point out what is important to consider when selecting which CRM to make first?</p> <p>Either bullet points or text.</p>	
<p>5. For each matrix selected above, please indicate the relevant polymers and concentration range you think would be appropriate in a CRM and why.</p>	<p>Matrix Choice 1 polymers and concentrations:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 2:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 3:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 4:</p>

<p>6. For each matrix indicated in Q2 above, please indicate the relevant polymers and particle size ranges you think would be appropriate in a CRM and why.</p> <p>Name any sources/suppliers of such polymer materials.</p>	<p>Matrix Choice 1 polymers and particle size ranges:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 2:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 3:</p> <p>Matrix Choice 4:</p>
<p>7. For which analytical method(s) should the CRMs be designed and why?</p> <p>Include comment on important technical requirements of the CRM per method and the stage of technical readiness of the methods listed.</p>	<p>Method Choice 1:</p> <p>Method Choice 2:</p> <p>Others:</p>
<p>8. List potential obstacles and challenges to producing matrix CRMs for MNPs.</p> <p>If possible, offer tips to mitigate these.</p>	

Do you have any other input that was not covered above? Additional feedback can be written below:

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